

Feeding the melting pot: agroecological urbanism for inclusive and sustainable food practices

Book of abstracts

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Table of Contents

Track 1: Social inclusion	5
Parallel session 1 – room 4.03	5
Building alliances for inclusive regional food systems: the comparison of Vitoria-Gasteiz and Preston	5
Analysing food democracy within university-led communities of practice: The case of the Stadsacademie	6
Coupling urban gardens and community kitchen to build agri-cultural community and food sovereignty: A case study from Ile-de-France region.	7
Parallel session 2 – room 4.03	8
Assessing food accessibility in rural areas: From a local food environment approach to a foodscape lens	8
Socio-spatial analysis of food poverty. A research in Turin	9
Farm Tours and their Public Pedagogies: Connecting to Nature, Foraging for Imaginaries	10
Parallel session 3 – room 4.03	11
Dachas and food democracy – ambivalent roles during times of crisis?	11
Outside the market, in tune with the seasons: diverse food economies of urban gardeners	12
The ‘Multifunctional Greenhouse’ in the making: Frugal innovation, bricolage, niche cultivation and re-purposing in peri-urban farming	13
Parallel session 4 – room 4.03	14
Building synergies around urban food poverty: The potential of collective and inclusive public facilities for food	14
Open innovation for the weekly food markets after the pandemic COVID_19	15
Multi-coded and collaboratively designed open spaces for shared food production (ONLINE POSTER PRESENTATION)	16
Track 2: Urban Agriculture	17
Parallel session 1 – room 4.04	17
Urban gardens in Bogotá: services and motivations beyond food production	17
Governance framework conditions hindering and supporting cooperative models for regional food supply	18
Urban pastoralism as nature based solution for a productive green infrastructure in the cities and their periphery	19
Parallel session 2 – room 4.04	20
Food insecurity among students and food justice. Example of a French University.	20
Social inclusion in local food planning of Nanjing, China	21
Urban Agriculture on the fringe. A relational approach to Urban Just transition in Valencia (Spain).	22
Parallel session 3 – room 4.04	23
Practicing urban agriculture positively influences household organic waste management habits – A quantitative study from Florianópolis, Brazil.	23
The hard work of reconnecting. Zooming in a local food initiative to investigate opportunities and barriers for a sustainable food system transformation.	24
Parallel session 4 – room 4.04	25
Where do you eat from? The role of Milanese SPGs in reducing the distance between the city and the countryside	25
Urban agriculture in Europe 2.0: An updated typology of urban and peri-urban agriculture in Europe	26
Overcoming urban issues through urban agriculture: Key benefits and some possible unwanted effects.	27

Track 3: urban planning, design & development	28
Parallel session 1 – room 4.02	28
The contribution of urban development projects to a food-enabling urbanism : analysis of two case-study in France	28
Relocalizing food production in times of crisis: Urban governance in Prague and Brno	30
Towards the scaling up of more agroecological and inclusive land practices in France.	31
Parallel session 2 – room 4.02	32
Evaluation of a Pilot for Transdisciplinary and Participatory Learning and Research for food system planning - AESOP4Food: Sustainable Food Planning Online Seminar and Living labs	32
The role of projects funded by the European Union in transforming the urban food system. The case of the FUSILLI project in Turin (Italy).	34
Exploring climate change, agriculture, and food planning nexus	35
Parallel session 3 – room 4.02	36
WORKSHOP: Sharing experiences of transdisciplinary practice in building sustainable city-region food systems	36
Parallel session 4 – room 4.02	38
Combining place-based and people-based approaches to assess food accessibility	38
Food and landscape. Evaluating the first year for a new Master Programme dealing with agroecological urbanism for inclusive and sustainable food practices.	39
The role of food gardening in addressing urban sustainability – a new framework for analysing policy approaches	40
Track 4: Food Governance	41
Parallel session 1 – room 4.08	41
The multiple and contested worlds of urban food governance: the case of the city of Valencia	41
The role of local food in municipal market policy: A snapshot of Michigan, USA and Kent County, England, England	42
Trans-local governance, meta-governance and agroecological urbanism. Some insights from Spain.	43
Parallel session 2 – room 4.08	44
From dairy-tankers to supermarket shelves: Orchestrating dairy supply chains in Strasbourg’s hinterland	44
Directionality in transition governance and innovation support for sustainable food systems: Towards a conceptual framework	45
Destabilizing the food regime “from within”: tools and strategies used by urban food policy actors	46
Parallel session 3 – room 4.08	47
Planning for the scaling up of the reterritorialisation of agricultural activities: insights from French case studies	47
Learning about, playing with, and experimenting in critical food futures using soft scenarios-- directions for food policy and planning	48
Municipal actors, hybrid governance and emergencies: Food system planning lessons from Toronto and elsewhere	49
Parallel session 4 – room 4.08	50
Pressure cooking in the melting pot: Integrated Landscape Approach for Foodscapes in the coastal area of Emilia Romagna	50
Towards healthy, sustainable and regional foodscapes: A landscape design perspective	51
Tourism Development and the Urbanization of Food Spaces: Changing Foodscapes in the Western Ligurian Riviera, Italy	52

Poster Presentations	53
INSUAH - Integrated Study on Urban Agriculture as Heritage	53
Self-production of food in Norman allotments: what contribution to the local food system?	55
What's cooking in Almere? Avoiding, adapting or adopting flavours from other cultures	56
Book Presentations	57
The Hybrid Governance of Urban Food Movements. Learning from Toronto and Brussels.	57
Small-Scale Soil-less Urban Agriculture in Europe	58
Urban Agricultural Heritage	59

Track 1: Social inclusion

Parallel session 1 – room 4.03

Building alliances for inclusive regional food systems: the comparison of Vitoria-Gasteiz and Preston

Tanya Zerbian

The rise of critical literature on local food initiatives has questioned their capacity to transform food systems (Cerrada-Serra et al., 2018; Tregear, 2011). As a result, scholars increasingly argue that local food initiatives should be understood from a process-based and relational perspective that acknowledges their potential as the result of their relations with others (Goodman et al., 2012). In particular, there is an increasing argument for integrating individual strategies to build collective power and jointly address social and environmental justice concerns. The collectivisation of individual local food initiatives' efforts is argued to lead to greater social integration and more inclusive place-making processes (Blay-Palmer et al., 2016; Holt-Gimenez & Schattuck, 2011). This is because alliance-building may support the construction of new meanings around local food and promote self-reflection to address current limitations for inclusive strategies if a diverse set of local food initiatives, particularly those formed by and for ethnic minority groups, are part of this process (Zerbian et al., 2022). In this context, studies are increasingly elucidating the challenges that prevent the formation of alliances that adopt a more holistic and culturally sensitive approach and integrate local food initiatives that cover production, distribution and consumption across diverse groups (Levkoe, 2014). This article aims to contribute to this emerging work by identifying the main challenges in forming regional food systems collectively. It applies a case study methodology including online semi-structured interviews, online participant observation, and document analysis to draw from lessons learnt from two cities (Preston, UK, and Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain). The comparison of both cases highlights that the collective building of regional food systems has two main barriers: limited resources, depoliticised reliance on food citizenship, and bifurcated conceptualisations of food questions. The presentation will elucidate how these challenges lead to the formation of two main networks of local food initiatives that do not necessarily seek to merge their strategies: one focusing on promoting localised food consumption to support rural farmers and another focusing on urban food poverty and food access. In discussing what this means for promoting agroecological urbanism, the presentation will point to possible pathways to surpass these limitations.

Analysing food democracy within university-led communities of practice: The case of the Stadsacademie

Steyaert A., Prové C., Dessein J.

Following the seminal work of Lang (1999), Hassanein further defined and operationalized the concept of food democracy (Hassanein, 2003, 2008) by establishing an analytical framework build on four key dimensions: (1) Becoming knowledgeable about food and the food system, (2) sharing ideas about the food system with others, (3) developing efficacy with respect to food and the food system and (4) acquiring an orientation toward the community good. As Hassanein (2003, p. 83) states “Food democracy ideally means that all members of an agro-food system have equal and effective opportunities for participation in shaping that system”. However, many of the studies that were published in the wake of her work (Baldy & Kruse, 2019; Davies, Cretella, & Franck, 2019; Hasson, 2019; Prost, Crivellaro, Haddon, & Comber, 2018; Sieveking, 2019) are set in a similar context. As a result the information we possess about operationalizing food democracy is limited to a small part of the members of the agro-food system. By focusing on topics such as urban agriculture, food policy councils and alternative food networks the majority of study subjects can be defined as “usual suspect” (white, middle-class and highly educated).

In this participatory action research, we want to counter this by focusing on two complex issues that inherently involve a culturally and socially diverse group of people (food redistribution and edible public space) and by working in two super-diverse communities in Ghent. By doing so, we hope to discover how food democracy can be operationalized in a more diverse context while also including the unusual suspects.

The research consists in setting up a trajectory within De Stadsacademie (Urban Academy, <https://stadsacademie.be/>) in which master students and promoters from different faculties work together with urban actors in a trans-disciplinary way to explore these issues from different perspectives. The involved students all write a master dissertation related to one of the issues. During this trajectory several sessions are organized in which inhabitants and local organizations co-create research questions, data collection and analysis strategies with the students and promoters involved. Based on the results these groups will also engage with local food policy makers and the food council of Ghent.

By using participatory observation, in-depth interviews, focus groups and arts-based methods we will observe if and how this trajectory helps to create equal and effective opportunities for participation of community residents. The four dimensions of food democracy mentioned above will guide us in this analysis.

Coupling urban gardens and community kitchen to build agri-cultural community and food sovereignty: A case study from Ile-de-France region.

Giacchè G., Provent F., Chapin Y., Aubry C.

The Urban Agriculture Chair supported by the AgroParisTech's Foundation aims to support the development of urban agriculture for cities resilience. The Chair develops a specific axis on "food accessibility for all" by coordinating a multi-actor network on "urban agriculture and food insecurity". The network, composed of social landlords, associations and NGOs, researchers, local authorities and so on, was launched based on two main findings: i- several AU projects are specialized in niche markets with high added value products tending to increase food inequalities in the city, ii-the food bank is not able to provide fresh products. Moreover, the health crisis of Covid19 has accelerated and amplified these dynamics both by exacerbating socio-environmental inequalities to food acces but also by strengthening solidarity networks in particular within community gardens (Schoen et al., 2021). Projects promoting access to food production plots (in particular the collective or family gardens) and/or processing (e.g. collective kitchens) have appeared to be very promising to improve food sovereignty (Marescot, 2020). However, the links between food production and processing still needs to be improved. An ongoing study has clearly shown the co-benefits of coupling of those activities (Giacchè and Baudelet, in press), particularly in socio-economic terms.

What implementation (by whom, which objectives and tools, what constraints and levers) is still necessary to improve food sovereignty?

We hypothesized that the association of self-production and collective food processing activities (as community kitchen) can lead to food sovereignty. On the one hand, the choice of planting could be made more in correspondence with eating habits of population (participating to the activities) and on the other hand it can contribute to an exchange of knowledge that leads to mutual enrichment.

To test this hypothesis, we jointly developed an action research project called PAM "du Potager A la Marmite" / "from garden to stock-pot" with the Laboratory - Soils, Knowledges, Flavors (Lab3S). This action aims to promote and develop projects combining community garden and collective kitchen within the municipality of Bondy, located in the north of Paris metropolitan region. We have involved local actors, in particular a cultural association working with precarious/fragile people, a municipal community center and an association working on food processing with refugees. We plan to present the method used to project co-construction with local partners (November 2021-April 2022) as well as the first feedback from the field survey carried out during the gardening and food processing activities (April 2022-July 2022).

Track 1: Social inclusion

Parallel session 2 – room 4.03

Assessing food accessibility in rural areas: From a local food environment approach to a foodscape lens

Claire Néel, Olivia Carbone, Coline Perrin, Christophe Soulard

This paper aims to assess food accessibility in a rural setting by articulating a place-based and a people-based approach through the case studies of three small localities located in the South of France (Hérault department). Interviews were conducted with residents, mayors and local food retailers, and were complemented with observation. The results show that analysing local food retail environments is insufficient because it does not take into account the significant role of informal food supply places and the high mobility of residents. Indeed, the foodscape lens demonstrates that individuals can navigate through several local food environments by developing various mobility strategies. Mobility thus appears as one of the main drivers of food accessibility in rural areas, with the economic and the social drivers.

Socio-spatial analysis of food poverty. A research in Turin

V. Allegretti, A. Toldo, C. Genova

The research, carried out as part of the Food Atlas of Torino project, aims to investigate the phenomenon of food poverty, focusing on the dimensions, forms, and dynamics that this condition assumes in the city of Torino (Italy). The general aim is to provide a theoretical advance in the scientific debate and propose policy indications for local institutions and actors. Over the past two years, the food poverty rate and its intensity have dramatically changed, exacerbating the conditions of those groups who are already experiencing deprivation, by eroding their ability to be protected from extreme vulnerability, due to the rising unemployment and other forms of income deprivation and rising prices of basic goods as well, due to the pandemic emergency and the Russia-Ukraine conflict. Following a multi-method research strategy, the study explores the three main dimensions of food poverty, the material, the social and the psycho-relational, using survey and qualitative interviews as main empirical sources. The data show the serious deterioration in the living conditions of the participants, the severe emotional burden that comes with poverty and the increase in new vulnerability profiles, such as in-work poverty and underemployment of college graduates. On a theoretical level, the study permits to contextualize the phenomenon, by tailoring the concept of food poverty to the Italian local case, within a multidimensional and multidisciplinary theorization.

Farm Tours and their Public Pedagogies: Connecting to Nature, Foraging for Imaginaries

Jesse Hsu

The 'Soil in the City' Project involves bringing community food project (CFP) members in Brighton and Hove, England, on a day visit to a regional farm. CFPS are network of social supermarkets, lunch clubs, and local food support schemes, supported by Brighton and Hove Food Partnership and other food organisations . During their visit, participants are intended to join activities such as farming and cooking experiences, therapy and leisure, and employability training. The project aspires to accomplish several educational, social, and political aims. The visits are assumed to nurture a connection between participants to the 'land' and local food production, develop food systems knowledge, and strengthen local food networks. Furthermore, disadvantaged groups are expected to gain some measure of control over the food system through the farm experience.

This paper explores the extent and nature of these claims by understanding the broad learning experiences of participants on the farm visits. Through participant observation and photographs of the six farm tours taking various CFPs and interviews with key stakeholders, this research uncovers the tensions between programmatic objectives and on-the-ground realities of the farm visits. Field notes, photographs, and interviews are analysed to understand the relationships between the farm tour structure, spaces, and practices; participant encounters; and narratives/knowledges. I focus especially on how the farm tour's spatial and programmatic structures afford and constrain various forms of learning. Extending previous academic literature framing farm tours as sites of environmental learning, this research considers the extent in which the public pedagogies of farm visits contribute to social and political outcomes desired by their organisers. By 'public pedagogies', I am adopting the perspective that everyday sites and encounters have educational salience, yet are arenas of discursive struggle.

Track 1: Social inclusion

Parallel session 3 – room 4.03

Dachas and food democracy – ambivalent roles during times of crisis?

L. Pungas

In the backdrop of multiple crises the role of global food systems demands urgent attention. In this context, the concept of food democracy is regarded simultaneously as a process towards, and as a desired outcome of, socially just and environmentally friendly food systems, shaped by active citizens.

In this article we will shed light on the aspects of food citizenship and food democracy within the practice of Food Self-Provisioning (FSP) in Eastern Estonia as our case study. Our empirical data is based on semi-structured interviews conducted in 2019-2021 with 45 persons on their so-called dachas - a Russian term for a plot of land with a seasonal allotment house, mostly used for food production. The analysis focuses on the three dimensions of food democracy (input, throughput, output) and explores to what extent can the FSP in the dachas serve as a vivid example of food democracy.

On the one hand FSP encompasses essential characteristics of food democracy, increases citizens' resilience and serves as an example of food sovereignty. On the other hand, it may weaken (food) democracy when serving as a basis for an escape

Outside the market, in tune with the seasons: diverse food economies of urban gardeners

Lucie Sovová, Petr Jehlička

Research concerned with more sustainable food provisioning has become more sensitive to the socio-economic relations underpinning the conventional food system as well as its alternatives. In this paper, we use Gibson-Graham's diverse economies framework to study food practices of urban gardeners in Brno, Czechia. Our exploration of the interactions between market-based, alternative and non-market food sources reveals that gardeners' food choices are strongly shaped by their engagement in food self-provisioning. Apart from providing a significant amount of harvest, food self-provisioning plays a key role in how other food sources are mobilized. Specifically, the gardens' natural seasonality establishes a temporal order which determines how and when different food sources are used. We thus expand the exploration of diverse food economies to a temporal dimension. We argue that the distinction between the agro-industrial system (where financial value is created through fast commodity circulation) and the agro-ecological system (where ecological care relates to slower natural processes) links to their time ontologies.

The 'Multifunctional Greenhouse' in the making: Frugal innovation, bricolage, niche cultivation and re-purposing in peri-urban farming

Ilja van Lammeren, Oane Visser and Willem Hulsink

Over the past decades, the landscape of greenhouse production in the Netherlands has changed dramatically through increased scale, ongoing specialisation and high-tech production. Diverging from this dominant monofunctional model, we can see many smaller producers selling or repurposing greenhouses for an array of non-agricultural purposes, ranging from caravan-stalling to bike-racing. This explorative paper examines the novel phenomena of Dutch growers' starting confined allotment gardens and self-pick orchards and theorizes these as an emerging model of multifunctional, peri-urban agriculture. To interpret the diversification strategies of these growers and to map the present shift in Dutch horticulture taking places at the fringes of the sector and the cities, we will work with the following sensitizing concepts (Blumer, 1954): frugal innovation, bricolage, repurposing and niche cultivation.

Drawing on larger qualitative research on (peri)urban agriculture in the Netherlands, this paper presents findings from 4 case studies from Westland and Oostland, prime greenhouse production regions located on the eastern- and western outskirts of Rotterdam-the Hague metropole. Situated amidst ever-more enclosed and automated monoculture greenhouse production, the case study growers retooled 'outdated' technological infrastructures and diversified, creating pockets of agro-ecological and social activity. What we entitle the 'multifunctional greenhouse', attracts surrounding rural and urban dwellers and ethnic minority groups in particular, whose engagement accelerates plant-biodiversity and knowledge-exchange inside the greenhouse and increases the availability of culturally appropriate foods in the wider region. Presenting initial research findings, we suggest the multifunctional greenhouse presents a promising alternative income model for Dutch growers and nurtures remarkably inclusive alternative food networks.

Track 1: Social inclusion

Parallel session 4 – room 4.03

Building synergies around urban food poverty: The potential of collective and inclusive public facilities for food

Simón-Rojo, Marian

Food insecurity and energy poverty are but two symptoms of deep-rooted systemic failures. In urban dense areas, the rising frequency of heat waves adds up to these problems. They pose the risk of turning some deprived neighbourhoods in Mediterranean-arid zones into pressure cookers. We look at both phenomena simultaneously to frame feasible and quick responses to adapt to these changing conditions, while exploring community-based solutions. We develop a case study in one of most deprived neighbourhoods in Madrid. We identify which factors of the urban environment and which elements in a public facility qualify to develop Centres for food culture (community kitchens). These centres are expected to host food-related actions that deploy as synergic satisfiers of different fundamental human needs: subsistence (food insecurity and energy poverty), protection, affection, creation, participation, identity, understanding, and leisure.

Open innovation for the weekly food markets after the pandemic COVID_19

Fava Nadia, Carrasco i Bonet Marta, Laganà Valentina Rosa, Nicolosi Agata Carmela

The Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated the search for innovative solutions throughout the food chain. Open innovation challenges must be resolved in line with current needs for food transitions according to the Farm and Fork strategy, which is included in the European Green Deal objectives to make food systems fair, healthy and environmentally friendly. The radical transformation of the food system under the banners of agroecology urbanism requires a reconfiguration of the social and cultural connection between agricultural producers, urban consumers and their relational and inclusive space. The purpose of this research is to recognize the adaptation and innovation mechanisms of the local food system over the last two years and, in particular, to identify sustainable practices at weekly food markets which could be used to foster the food transition. A total of 149 semi-open questionnaires were given to food market vendors and factor analysis was used to highlight latent factors and how much the open market is rooted in the territory. The results shows that a territorial approach can foster “innovation” in these traditional weekly food markets, which otherwise could lose their social potential for food transition.

**Multi-coded and collaboratively designed open spaces for shared food production
(ONLINE POSTER PRESENTATION)**

Caroleen Mees

Commonly used and collaboratively designed open spaces for shared food production are anchor points in the city – multi-coded urban resources that provide possible responses to the consequences of urbanization and climate change, as well as to the presence of social and cultural differences.

The paper’s analysis is framed in a transdisciplinary food planning perspective focusing on the investigation of the impact of shared open spaces as a productive urban landscape in the neighborhood and city scale. The exploration concentrates on the potential benefits, tensions, and trade-offs of “add-ons” in these urban open spaces: spatial components for the production of food, water, energy and materials, as well as for the creation of economic and social resources. The paper asks if these added spatial elements - in their capacity for activation of urban space and for the creation of conflict - establish more resilient and sustainable urban spaces, respond to the various needs and preferences of residents and foster exchange with the surrounding urban environment. The intention is to investigate in this context the diversity of add-ons from a micro- to macro-perspective to derive strategies for collaboratively designed, multi-coded shared urban spaces for food production at the intersection of architecture and open space planning.

Track 2: Urban Agriculture

Parallel session 1 – room 4.04

Urban gardens in Bogotá: services and motivations beyond food production

Manente V., Silvio Caputo

This paper takes its cue from a PhD fieldwork investigation that gathered detailed information for 15 urban gardens in Bogotá together with a large dataset developed by the Bogotá Botanical Garden to further explore the values and motivations that bring people to grow food in this city. The database includes 1,216 private and community gardens over the entire urban area, hence representing a unique opportunity to evaluate motivations for urban food production for diverse communities. The analysis of the database followed by a comparison with the fieldwork findings enables the identification of clusters of urban farmers, defined by aims behind their practices and socio-economic conditions. It offers a nuanced understanding of the role of urban agriculture in this context and contributes to further define food security.

Governance framework conditions hindering and supporting cooperative models for regional food supply

Andreas Obersteg, Jörg Knieling

From a perspective of the municipal level framework conditions for municipalities to support the shift to regionalized and more sustainable food systems are examined. Thematic focusses are the topics safeguard and access to agricultural land and the support of short food chains through public tendering and community catering.

Urban pastoralism as nature based solution for a productive green infrastructure in the cities and their periphery

Triboi R. M.

The pastoral practice, a subsistence pattern characterized by 'common' in property and management, decade starting the industrial era because of its low productivity and concurrency with intensified agriculture, industry, urban functions and infrastructure, due, in the last decades, to urban sprawl.

Today, the animal production sector is dominated by an intensive and industrial model that negatively impacts the global health (animal, environmental and human). The intensification of the pastoral activity is difficult because of the interdependence between the shepherd, animals and environment and its survival in almost initial form is related to its independence from mechanization and urban infrastructure.

The aggressive urbanization of the last decades generated an important quantity of abandoned land especially in the periphery of the cities and offered shepherds unexpected opportunities in times of uncertainty to extend their activity. The adaptation of this practice to urban context has a diverse management formula across European Union, because of different approaches (based on the traditional form, encourage by contemporary activism).

In the Balkans, the persistence of pastoral practice and its short and medium transhumance infrastructure is strongly related to the strategy of avoiding state management and the tradition of alternative food networks.

The quantitative research of this study concerned mainly the periphery of Bucharest, although some interviews, data analysis and visit were made also in Parisian metropolitan area (France) and Wageningen (Netherlands).

The analysis of different typologies of urban shepherding permitted the identification of patterns of activity that could sustain developing a more sustainable and resilient model of urban pastoralism in today's context.

Innovative aspects like complex management plan for marketing and communicating on the activity, local actors' inclusion in the co-construction process of the project, connection to local food networks are important features of the western model of today urban pastoralism that support its development. The main challenges revolve around the dissemination of the "know-how" and accepting the pastoral activity as way of life (breeding animals in extensive system implies a way of life not compatible with current expectations of working conditions).

Track 2: Urban Agriculture

Parallel session 2 – room 4.04

Food insecurity among students and food justice. Example of a French University.

Léna Jégat

During the health crisis linked to Covid-19, the French media highlighted the problem of precariousness, particularly food insecurity (numerous reports in food distributions). The student population then stands out as particularly precarious.

The calculation of the household vulnerability index to food insecurity in Caen's neighborhoods led us to focus the study on the student population, which appears to be particularly vulnerable. Our working hypothesis is then to question the food practices of the student population through the prism of their social origins.

Among the results, a spatial analysis of the "food mile" based on the census of food stores allowed us to learn that the neighborhoods with the fewest stores are those with a large student population.

The results analysis of a large survey of students on their eating habits identified several student consumption profiles (lunch/dinner practices). Finally, the students' food insecurity seems to be depending on urban morphology and on the integration of the student population in the city of Caen.

Social inclusion in local food planning of Nanjing, China

Luoman Zhao

This study analyses the features of top-down local food planning initiatives and their impact on social inclusion in the case of Nanjing. Firstly, it discusses planning initiatives that involve vulnerable groups in local food supply chains, including production, marketing, and consumption. Secondly, the impacts and challenges of local food supply chains on social inclusion under the influence of these planning initiatives are analysed. Finally, suggestions for local food planning toward social inclusion are proposed. This study argues that current local food planning positively impacts social inclusion. Indicators in local food planning, such as the lowest limit of arable land area, urban food self-sufficiency rate, food accessibility, and food affordability, can help disadvantaged groups, especially low-income consumers. But current food localization plans ignore the bottom-up initiatives that contribute to social inclusion. Therefore, local food planning could encourage various urban agriculture activities like social farming and community gardening and provide a formalization and legalization path for informal urban food production and informal local food markets to involve diversified groups.

Urban Agriculture on the fringe. A relational approach to Urban Just transition in Valencia (Spain).

Vilasis-Pamos J., Lozano-Sarzosa SM, Mascarell-Correcher E., Aranguiz-Mesias P., Zerbian T., Palau-Salvador G.

This paper analyzes urban agriculture as a path for development towards a Just Transition within the environment in which it operates. We interviewed several individual initiatives, as well as most of the collective initiatives within Valencia's urban agriculture. The preliminary analysis of the results indicates that all the initiatives have a common component: to maintain the traditional relationship with the Valencian orchard, to defend sustainable form of consumption and a lifestyle that the current global political and economic paradigm has abandoned. In addition, the urban agriculture of Valencia seeks to generate a change in how we relate to the environment. This will ensure that our passage through the planet is fairer and more sustainable.

Track 2: Urban Agriculture

Parallel session 3 – room 4.04

Practicing urban agriculture positively influences household organic waste management habits – A quantitative study from Florianópolis, Brazil.

Gianluca Di Fiore; Kathrin Specht; Cesare Zanasi; Oscar José Rover

Proper organic waste management practices are crucial for limiting its negative environmental and health impacts. Among the several organic waste treatment strategies, composting it for urban agriculture (UA) use has become increasingly popular. The present paper is then analyzing how practicing UA in influences citizens' household organic waste management behaviors in the city of Florianópolis, Brazil. The results showed a strong positive influence of practicing UA on self-composting and thereby highlighted the role of such practice in sensitizing urban residents to waste management issues and supporting local organic waste management strategies.

The hard work of reconnecting. Zooming in a local food initiative to investigate opportunities and barriers for a sustainable food system transformation.

Mattia Andreola, Francesca Forno

The paper proposes an approach that combines the multi-level perspective and the theory of social practice in the study of a community supporting agriculture in Trentino to critically understand the innovative and transformative potential of such an experience by investigating the reasons behind its creation and the crisis it is currently going through. The two approaches have mostly been considered antithetical to understanding the complexity of socio-technical change. However, through this analysis, we want to argue in favour of their complementary showing how they mutually reinforce each other's understanding of sustainable innovations. In particular, we identify an intersection between regimes and practices that constrain the transition towards sustainability and that local governments should consider in their planning.

Track 2: Urban Agriculture

Parallel session 4 – room 4.04

Where do you eat from? The role of Milanese SPGs in reducing the distance between the city and the countryside

Cecilia Cornaggia

The AFNs are food supply chains opposing the mainstream agri-food system, which is highly industrialized and globalized. AFNs can foster change in different ways, among which reconnecting consumers and producers from the same territory. Given these premises, the present study investigates the role of SPGs, a form of AFN typical of the Italian context, in reducing the city-country distance. The investigation, which adopted a mixed methods approach, focused on the territory of Milan, an area in which high degrees of urbanization coexist with the presence of South Milan Agricultural Park, the largest agricultural park in Europe, where approximately 1400 farms are located. The results show that, due to historical-cultural reasons, the role of SPGs in reducing the distance between city and country is marginal. However, the action of some SPGs in partnership with other local entities has brought about interesting changes, which deserve further study.

Urban agriculture in Europe 2.0: An updated typology of urban and peri-urban agriculture in Europe

Jan Eelco Jansma, Esther Veen

Urban and peri-urban Agriculture (UA) is not a new phenomenon: it has co-existed in and co-evolved with urbanisation ever since the expansion of early human conurbations. Today, many cities in Europe have re-discovered UA as a contributor to a more healthy and sustainable urban environment. However, UA still has not unfolded its potential due to (societal, political and spatial) barriers resulting from gaps in knowledge, expertise and advocacy. A clear typology is instrumental in identifying, understanding and acknowledging the potential of UA at different levels of policy making. Many typologies have been issued in literature last decades, yet, it lacks an overarching typology that steps beyond the local and national perspective, and that includes promising innovations like vertical farming. Moreover, labels often used do not distinguish clearly between the different ways in which urban agriculture is performed. This paper offers a comprehensive overview to urban agriculture. It characterised UA in Europe based on interviews with experts in the field representing eleven European countries (n=16; representing 10 countries in Europe) and an online questionnaire about characteristics and dimensions of UA initiatives (n=112; representing 18 countries in Europe). The results propose six different UA typologies, i.e.: (1) Urban farm, (2) Zero acreage farm, (3) Social Farm, (4) Do-It-Yourself garden/farm (5) Community park, and (6) Community garden. Although this paper presents these typologies as distinctive entities, it is important to underline that these inevitably are a simplification of reality. In real-life UA is highly diverse, an overlap in the proposed typologies exists, with various combinations of characteristics possible. Moreover, this paper offers a snapshot of UA of today, knowing that the field of modern UA is highly dynamic. However, the suggested typology gives structure to the apparent diversity of UA in Europe and thus is instrumental to piecemeal disclose the potential of UA in Europe.

Overcoming urban issues through urban agriculture: Key benefits and some possible unwanted effects.

Gottero E., Cassatella C.

The benefits of Urban Agriculture (UA) are manifold and concern different spheres of urban sustainability. If properly addressed, UA can contribute significantly to the achievement of the main goals of urban agendas. In this paper the authors present an overview of the key benefits and unwanted effects of UA, including tools to evaluate them, the main relationships with different UA forms, as well as how UA can address many urban policy themes.

Track 3: urban planning, design & development

Parallel session 1 – room 4.02

The contribution of urban development projects to a food-enabling urbanism : analysis of two case-study in France

Paula Macé Le Ficher

The extended abstract will present the results of two case studies conducted as part of a PhD research about interactions between urban food systems relocation dynamics, and contemporary changes in urbanism, in the French context. Our observation point is urban development, considered here as the institutionnalised process involving a specific system of actors – real estate developers, architects, programmers, engineering consultants... interlinked with city governments and, to a lesser extent, with urban citizens – which materialises as urban development projects (Arab, 2018). The design of these new urban areas is undepinned by concerns and standarts, among wich food – and food sustainability – appears to be gaining visibility, suggesting a transforming potential both for urban food systems and urban development processes (Bognon et al., 2018 ; Morgan, 2009). Entering the debate polarized between the sceptics, who point out the ‘greenwashing’ tendency of a neoliberal urbanism, and the enthusiasts, who foresee a mutual reinvention of food and the city, our research contributes to exploring the place of food in the making of urban spaces (Brand et al., 2017 ; Cabannes and Marocchino, 2018 ; Marot, 2020 ; Parham, 2015) through an in-depth analysis of two urban development projects in which food is a core issue. In the outskirts of Paris, ‘Base 217’ consists in the renewal of a former military airbase, including many economic activities and a large organic urban farm runned by a collective of local market gardeners. In Nantes, ‘Doulon-Gohards’ is a functional mix of housing, activities and 4 small farms runned by new farmers. Based on documentary analyses and inteviews with stakeholders involved in each project, we notice that beyond their specifics, common features emerge. Firstly, city governments and public planners appear to play a leading role in enabling producers to start and develop their activities, through land-control, networking of local stakeholders, and political and financial support in the settlement process. Secondly, a new food expertise arises in urban development processes, from cross-fertilisation with alternative food networks. Thirdly, these projects represent demonstration areas that foster city-scale food strategies. However, these evolutions must not hide the difficulties to include civil society and specially disadvantaged populations, both in the decision-making process and in the benefits of the projects : the ambitions set out on terms of democratic access to food products stumble on rather small production volumes and expensive prices.

Relocalizing food production in times of crisis: Urban governance in Prague and Brno

M. Pixová, C. Plank

The multitude of ongoing crises has exposed an increasing need for local food alternatives, which we conceptualize as values-based modes of production and consumption (VPC). Drawing on our research of the role of VPC in the Czech national food regime, we analyse how different VPC are supported in urban governance and planning in two Czech metropolises, Prague and Brno. In these cities' strategies and plans, urban food policy is a new phenomenon and not yet consistent with other urban agendas. Moreover, it is preoccupied with food production's environmental and aesthetic aspects rather than food provisioning itself. Support for community gardens and a lack of attention for traditional food self-provisioning such as allotment gardening, whose food production potential is far higher, indicate that urban food policy in Prague and Brno is not based on knowledge of the role of VPC in the Czech national food regime and misunderstands the different potential of VPC to produce food within it.

Towards the scaling up of more agroecological and inclusive land practices in France.

Coline PERRIN

Farmland is currently attracting new societal and scientific interest. Its management is presented as a cornerstone for adapting agriculture to societal expectations concerning food, landscape and the environment. I analyse how these issues shape local public action on farmland and trigger local innovations in the South of France (Hérault). I focus on the rationales, instruments and partners of local authorities' land strategies. Forward-thinking province-based policy on fragile natural areas in the 1980s led to the establishment of vast public open green spaces for recreational activities, managed partially using agroecological methods. Since 2000, inter-municipal authorities have contributed to the scaling of farmland innovations, allowing for their replication (scaling out), their institutionalisation (scaling up) and the dissemination of new principles of land management (scaling deep). Finally, I highlight the importance of individuals and socio-political power relations in these innovation pathways. My results suggest avenues for critical analyses of innovations in farmland management, for research on the spatial coexistence of agricultural and food models and more broadly on the land-food nexus.

Track 3: urban planning, design & development

Parallel session 2 – room 4.02

Evaluation of a Pilot for Transdisciplinary and Participatory Learning and Research for food system planning - AESOP4Food: Sustainable Food Planning Online Seminar and Living labs

Roxana Maria Triboi, Jeroen de Vries, Damien Conaré, Michiel Dehaene, Marian Simón Rojo, Maciej Lepkowski, Aleksandra Nowysz, Anna Podlasek, Marzena Tomaszewska

"Planning for sustainable food production, food resilience, food justice and food security is more than ever urging us to look for more effective, equitable, and just approaches that radically change not only the way we grow food, but the very core of our living space. There is evidence of serious gaps in knowledge and transformative competences to address the challenges in a transdisciplinary way and the recognition of the essential role of graduates of (spatial) planning course in developing integrated territorial plans in a democratic way, and understanding an inter-sectoral, multi-level, and multi-stakeholder approach.

Therefore, the Erasmus plus Action for Education, Spatial Organisation and Planning for Sustainable Food (AESOP4Food), a partnership of universities and NGOs from Belgium, France, the Netherlands, Poland, and Spain aims to answer the need for sustainable food planning by creating a joint interdisciplinary European learning activity. Core target groups are university staff and students from architecture, urban planning, landscape architecture, agronomy, environmental sciences, as well as sustainability studies. Secondary audiences are NGOs and communities involved in local food systems, municipalities and the wider public, in order to break down barriers and foster collaboration, while encouraging knowledge development at all levels: personal, professional, communal and political.

In the first half of 2022, AESOP4Food organised a seminar and supported the development of living labs. The online seminar is a combination of lectures, interactive exercises, tailor made assignments and presentations by the participants. The seminar is supported by a Wiki with learning outcomes, exercises, assignments, references. It makes use of interactive digital tools such as Mural.co, and Padlet.

The partnership between academic institutions, staff with civil society (NGOs and communities), and local authorities is supported by the Participatory Action Learning and Action Research (PALAR) nature of the project and the connected living labs. This allows knowledge to be cocreated rather than simply transferred top-down to communities and connect it to local circumstances and needs.

The paper presents the outline of the online-seminar in connection with a series of living labs and the findings of the evaluation of the first pilot seminar. We would like to discuss our findings, and the feasibility of carrying out the PALAR approach in an online mode.

The role of projects funded by the European Union in transforming the urban food system. The case of the FUSILLI project in Turin (Italy).

Federico Cuomo; Luca Battisti; Giacomo Pettenati; Egidio Dansero

Several EU framework programs focus on promoting the sustainable transformation of urban food systems.

Among them, the Horizon 2020 project, FUSILLI, is ongoing in Turin (Italy) with the aim of enhancing the urban food system by testing experimental policies in governance, production, consumption and distribution activities. These policies are expected to be mobile or capable of being transferred and replicated in very different contexts.

Starting from the case-study analysis in Turin, this paper aims to highlight the main pros and cons of the EU funded projects related to food policy mobility.

The results underline the importance of those projects in helping municipalities in implementing food policies and proposing experimental activities that can be successfully replicated across very different urban contexts.

Exploring climate change, agriculture, and food planning nexus

Cecília Delgado

This paper explores the following questions: (1) to what extent Climate Adaptive Plans and Strategies – CAPEs – include the increase of local food production as a way to address the effects of climate change; (2) Do they consider each step of the food chain or solely food production; (3) How those measures are transcribed to the planning rules and regulations. A selected group of 14 cities that entered a Portuguese competition ECO XXI aiming to measure city sustainability achievements was used for empirical examination. Results suggest that adaptive measures relate to increasing local agriculture, mapping out land availability or stress the need for local agroecological practices. Moreover, CAPEs measures are predominantly related to agriculture production, leaving behind subsequent food chain activities. Central conclusion is that even if those measures are, in theory, to be transcribed into planning rules and regulations in coming years, they remain fragile to transform reality: planner’s awareness to these topics remain insufficient and the links between food, climate and planning are still missing, or else quite thin.

Track 3: urban planning, design & development

Parallel session 3 – room 4.02

WORKSHOP: Sharing experiences of transdisciplinary practice in building sustainable city-region food systems

Anna Wissmann, Henk Renting

The workshop will bring together researchers and planners to share their experiences of taking part – as scientists and stakeholders - in local multi-stakeholder processes aiming to build short food value chains, create food strategies and policy and (re-)construct sustainable city region food systems. We will discuss the various roles scientists may play in this field, their potential contributions and successful modes of collaboration, but also examine the structural constraints on transdisciplinary work resulting from the way “doing science” is organised today. The workshop a.o. builds on research and policy experiences collected in the European EFUA and FoodE projects.

The workshop will be in an open format, starting with a short storytelling phase where both invited speakers and participants with relevant experience will share their personal experience and insights on:

- Who they worked with
- What their common goal was
- What their own role(s) were; as scientists, and possibly as representatives of a research institution
- How they positioned themselves, and were perceived and positioned by their collaborators
- Difficulties they faced, especially in making the multi-stakeholder collaboration work
- Success factors they can identify – these could be certain modes of working together, constellations of actors, values and attitudes, but also external circumstances like larger societal and political processes, the availability of (research) funding.

The main part of the workshop will be devoted to drawing out the shareable lessons from these specific experiences. We will discuss to what extent there is a potential for transfer or if each situation is ultimately unique in its circumstances and its set of actors with their individual resources and degrees of freedom, but also their personalities and mutual relationships. Multi-stakeholder processes are often described as a set of organisations from different sectors collaborating, but in practice, organisations are always made up of, and represented by individual people, creating a different dynamic each time. The question of process design and designability, and the role scientists may play in this, will be raised.

The workshop will be the length of one of the parallel sessions. The physical setup of the room would ideally not be theatre-style but rather a circular form more conducive to interaction.

Track 3: urban planning, design & development

Parallel session 4 – room 4.02

Combining place-based and people-based approaches to assess food accessibility

S. Vonthron, C. Perrin, M. Perignon, P. Rollet, C. Méjean, C.T. Soulard

Food deserts designate neighbourhoods with low availability and accessibility of healthy foods. In France, there have been very few studies of food deserts, a gap which this paper aims to fill. Moreover, we address the frequently ignored daily mobility of inhabitants, conducting our study in the Montpellier city-region. First, we estimated the population living far from food outlets and mapped the related residential areas. Second, we explored whether households' food environment exposure varies with socioeconomic position, basing our analysis on the 699 household cross-sectional study Mont'Panier. We find that deprived households are not those most affected by physical access issues. In addition, the deprived households located farthest from food stores are not living in the most deprived neighbourhoods. Considering daily mobility modifies this result: households living in the most deprived neighbourhoods are exposed to fewer and less diverse food outlets in their daily activity spaces than households living in wealthier neighbourhoods. These results confirm the need to go beyond place-based approaches and develop people-based approaches.

Food and landscape. Evaluating the first year for a new Master Programme dealing with agroecological urbanism for inclusive and sustainable food practices.

Ingrid Sarlöv-Herlin, Anna Peterson, Love Silow

This paper presents and discuss the development and learning methods of a cross-disciplinary Master's programme "Food and Landscape" at SLU, Alnarp Sweden, embracing the topic of this conference; 'Agroecological urbanism for inclusive and sustainable food practices'. The programme covers the relation between food, people and places as well as how urban and rural landscapes can be planned, designed and maintained from a sustainability perspective, viewed through a food lens. The programme also combines the cross disciplinary, synthesising and place-related approach of landscape architecture with the understanding of the role of food from a broad cultural and critical perspective that characterises the subject food studies. Students participating in the programme will have the opportunity to learn tools and methods for strategic planning, design, entrepreneurship, management and communication centred round the food landscape as a part of sustainable development, covering all aspects from local to global. The programme hence takes a holistic approach and relates the content to the 17 UN's global development goals. During the first year, students acquire knowledge about the scientific scope that characterises the interface between landscape studies and the international, multidisciplinary subject food studies. During year 2, progression increases through more problematisation in a globally focused course. This is followed by an applied project task in groups, with method studies and strategic solutions to food and landscape-related challenges. The programme concludes with a degree project which can consist of either cross-disciplinarily applied case studies or deepened theoretical studies of a food/landscape-related subject.

In this paper, we summarizes and analysed the outcome of the first year of the programme. What expectations did we have, what challenges did we foresee, and which were the real challenges that turned out? In writing up the extended abstract, we will, together with own experiences and reflections be using comments and evaluations from programme students. One outcome for the first year was a bigger international range of students than expected and challenges and advantages related to this. Other aspects are the differences in previous learning experiences and methods between for example Swedish and some international students. For example is the learning method 'literature seminars' very well known to Swedish student, while an unknown and sometimes unclear experience to some of the international students.

The role of food gardening in addressing urban sustainability – a new framework for analysing policy approaches

Ingrid Jahrl, Joëlle Salomon Cavin

The aim of this paper is to develop a new framework to analyse governance mechanisms, expressed as policy approaches to urban food garden development, which can serve as an analytical tool to enable comparison of cities and to analyse their efforts to achieve urban sustainability. The framework is based on case study analysis of public policies towards urban food gardening in the Swiss cities Berne, Lausanne and Zurich. We identified three core dimensions to characterise policy approaches in cities for the further development of city gardening: frames, level of institutionalisation, and policy-society relationship. Frames refer to the perception of gardening which is expressed by the objectives set by urban policy and the contributions gardening should fulfil in urban development. Level of institutionalisation provides information on the extent to which garden support is anchored in urban policy. Policy-society relationship refers to the type of leadership by city politics and the possibility for non-political actors to participate. For the further development of urban food gardening, the challenge for urban planners is to find the best possible combination of the three elements for their cities, adapted to the respective city context, the dominant sustainability goals and the social actors involved.

Track 4: Food Governance

Parallel session 1 – room 4.08

The multiple and contested worlds of urban food governance: the case of the city of Valencia

A. Escario-Chust, T. Zerbian, S. Segura-Calero, G. Palau-Salvador

Cities have positioned themselves as key actors in agri-food sustainability transitions through the implementation of food policy councils and urban food strategies. By promoting participatory food policymaking, these spaces allow several actors to engage in a contested process of mutual learning that challenges individual paradigms and helps construct a common goal. Significantly, the development of these mechanisms has meant that alternative food networks have had the possibility of reclaiming power in governance spaces and thus contribute to sustainability transitions. Nevertheless, while signalling that transitions governance can bring more inclusive and collective change, critical studies call for the need of paying attention to power dynamics in these processes. Drawing from this notion, the paper explores how diverse sets of governance actors mobilise and execute power within and between two urban food governance processes – an agri-food transition platform and a food policy council – in Valencia, Spain. In doing so, the paper raises three main points to further understand the potential of urban food governance processes for sustainability transitions: the longitudinal and cross-scale evaluation of power dynamics and subsequent tensions, the acknowledgement of different kinds of power, and the analysis of the tensions derived from the coexistence of governance spaces.

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The role of local food in municipal market policy: A snapshot of Michigan, USA and Kent County, England, England

Amanda Maria Edmonds

are a popular sustainable local food system strategy, offering transparency and connection between eaters and growers while strengthening the agricultural economy, reducing food miles, increasing healthy food access, fostering entrepreneurship, and revitalizing neighbourhoods. In the last twenty years, the number of farmers markets has increased considerably in both the US and Europe. Municipalities play crucial roles in markets including through regulating their land use and permitting. Yet, very little scientific scholarship has examined how markets fit into municipal plans and policy, representing a large research gap for such a longstanding, visible anchor of urban life and food provisioning. This study examined whether farmers markets are codified in municipal plans and law through cases in southeast England and the US state of Michigan. It found a vast underrepresentation of markets in policy and plans in both places. This can have negative implications for the ability to start and sustain farmers markets.

Trans-local governance, meta-governance and agroecological urbanism. Some insights from Spain.

Daniel López-García, Marian Simón-Rojo

The present communication aims to address the role of multi-actor processes of knowledge generation within agroecological urbanism, through the application of the concepts of trans-local governance and meta-governance. For this purpose we analyse the outcomes of a Working Group on Agroecological Planning within the Spanish Network of Municipalities for Agroecology. We have collected primary information through participant observation and selected online surveys to the group's participants, and we have analysed the minutes of the working group. Our results point out the ability of the different profiles and disciplinary backgrounds for opening comprehensive approaches to urbanism that are at the same time innovative and applied to trans-local realities and needs. Cooperation and complementation between different local realities and positions set possibilities for different actors that feel isolated or with scarce resources to develop innovative and comprehensive thinking; and to develop creative, holistic and ready-to-use solutions for relevant issues regarding agroecological urbanism.

Track 4: Food Governance

Parallel session 2 – room 4.08

From dairy-tankers to supermarket shelves: Orchestrating dairy supply chains in Strasbourg's hinterland

Romane Joly

Many dairy products consumed in urban centres originate from long food supply chains. This paper examines the circulation of dairy in the hinterland of Strasbourg. It focuses on the socio-material infrastructure co-produced by dairy operators and mass retailing that orchestrates food supply chains. The research is based on a qualitative approach of urban metabolism that examines the social arrangements and material supports that determine circulations. The data set originates from analysis of interviews with dairy stakeholders and grey literature. In the paper, we demonstrate that dairy operators and mass retailing determine the production of dairy and channel supply chains up to urban distribution sites from the far and the near. In this sense, the socio-material infrastructure for circulation contributes to reshaping the hinterland in response to urban demands.
Circulation, infrastructure, urban metabolism

Directionality in transition governance and innovation support for sustainable food systems: Towards a conceptual framework

P. Nielsen

With the aim of improving analyses of sustainable food system transition, this short paper contributes to the discussion of transition barriers. The paper reviews strands of literature on sustainability transitions, on human-nature relationships and on transition governance to discuss elements relating to directionality and diversity of transition initiatives and innovations. It concludes by presenting three dimensions for further research towards a conceptual framework for transition governance in food systems: the plurality and diversity of transition initiatives and innovations stemming from varying human-nature relationships, the way this plurality is enacted through different sustainability discourses and what role this plurality can play in transition governance. The short paper is part of ongoing PhD research.

Destabilizing the food regime “from within”: tools and strategies used by urban food policy actors

Mattioni D., Milbourne P., Sonnino R.

In the context of food transition studies scant attention has been given to the role of food regime actors – particularly state authorities (be they local or national) - in introducing novelties to, and destabilizing aspects of, the dominant food regime. Specifically, little is known about how state-based regime actors use the power at their disposal to bring about change “from within”. Using data from qualitative research with local government actors in 10 European cities, this paper provides a detailed exploration of the actions of these actors in reshaping urban food agendas. What emerges from our research is that changes and innovations that question the regime’s status quo can emerge from within the regime. Local authorities have reoriented material and discursive resources and tools towards a new way of doing and conceiving food founded on the values of care, trust and solidarity.

Track 4: Food Governance

Parallel session 3 – room 4.08

Planning for the scaling up of the reterritorialisation of agricultural activities: insights from French case studies

Tianzhu. Liu, Romain. Melot, Frédéric. Wallet

Food planning as a new type of local policy aims at shaping the local food system. An essential component of the local food system is the reterritorialisation of agricultural activities (RAA). RAA consists of reinforcing local food production and its diversification activities oriented toward local consumers. Currently, there is no systematic investigation on food planning approaches to RAA. This study fills this gap by assessing the place of RAA and associated policy instruments in 29 French food planning projects. France is particular in that the state defines food planning by national law and emphasises its objective of improving the agricultural economy and structuring local supply chains. Results show that RAA has a leading place in French food plans; improving food production and local supply chains are goals targeted by a large number of food planning projects. These projects have leveraged diverse instruments to improve RAA, showing a focus on facilitating professional farmers' transition and frequently applied strategies in the previously neglected field, namely middle-stage local food infrastructure. We conclude by emphasising that the French experience may give insights to other countries in developing strategies to scale up RAA but have to be adapted based on contexts and institutional settings.

Learning about, playing with, and experimenting in critical food futures using soft scenarios-- directions for food policy and planning

Steven R. McGreevy, Christoph D. D. Rupprecht, Norie Tamura, Kazuhiko Ota, Mai Kobayashi, Maximilian Spiegelberg

Imagining sustainable food futures is key to effectively transforming food systems. Yet even transdisciplinary approaches struggle to open up complex and highly segregated food policy governance for co-production. Here we argue that soft scenarios are vital transdisciplinary tools that empower societal stakeholders to broaden possible food system trajectories through learning about, playing with and experimenting with critical food futures. Specifically, soft scenarios contribute in four ways: 1) questioning widely held assumptions about the future; 2) being inclusive to multiple perspectives and worldviews; 3) fostering receptiveness to unimaginable futures; 4) developing futures literacy. Using cases from the FEAST Project, narratives, serious games, interactive art, and models demonstrate how future scenarios can provide a transdisciplinary space for engagement and how agency, policy change, and scale interact in scenario co-creation processes for food policy. In order to overcome the highly-segregated nature of food policy governance, evidence from these cases shows that soft scenario methods can build consensus among disparate stakeholders and bring to the fore critical perspectives necessary for fostering sustainable food systems.

Municipal actors, hybrid governance and emergencies: Food system planning lessons from Toronto and elsewhere

Joe Nasr, Jenelle Regnier-Davies

Municipal staff and decision makers have a long but patchy history of involvement in anticipating potential emergencies and, even more, in addressing the impacts of emergencies. However, the impacts of emergencies on food systems was largely left out from the planning for emergencies' impacts on urban systems; moreover, responses to emergencies are typically managed by offices of emergency management or disaster relief agencies, without anchoring responses in food system planning approaches. Conversely, the rise of food system planning as an interest area for planners and other urban actors has generally not focused on the role of sudden disruptions, whether 'natural' disasters, wars or epidemics.

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted a number of deficiencies in the global food system as well as deficiencies that are grounded in the urban context – as food advocates have long warned (Raja 2020). Municipal actors have played a critical role in responding to this massive disruption, including the resulting urban food system shocks. In parallel, dramatic shifts occurred in the work of community-based food system actors. These shifts not only challenged both sets of actors – they also enabled new modes of operation, new flexibility, and new forms of collaboration (Cohen 2022; Jones, Hill and Beardmore 2022). This moment and space highlighted possibilities for a 'hybrid governance' of urban food systems (Manganelli 2022).

This presentation considers the roles and perspectives of key municipal actors in anticipating emergencies in relation to urban food systems, and particularly, in responding to such emergencies. It focuses on municipal actors in Toronto, comparing their experiences with those in four other large cities – Vancouver, Baltimore, New York City and Milan. We examine what municipal preparedness (if any) was in place for responding to the impacts of major emergencies on local food systems, and where food system planning may have laid a foundation for responses during COVID-19. We then focus on the current pandemic to analyze how the hybrid responses that were rapidly put in place in different cities related to the pre-existing food-system planning frameworks in place. The presentation concludes with reflections on how municipal actors can help better connect food system planning and emergency planning by applying a 'food lens' to the work of a wide range of municipal actors (City of Toronto 2019), while highlighting how the synergy seen in the hybrid governance during a crisis can inform the work of municipal actors beyond the emergency mode provided by the pandemic.

Track 4: Food Governance

Parallel session 4 – room 4.08

Pressure cooking in the melting pot: Integrated Landscape Approach for Foodscapes in the coastal area of Emilia Romagna

Jeroen de Vries, Meryem Atik, Roxana Triboi, Giovanni Barbotti, Sebastian Burgos Guerrero, Jiaqi Yang, Kelan Li, Arina Pautova, Arati Uttur

In 2022 the LE:NOTRE Institute organised a four days landscape forum in Rimini, on the coast of the Regione Emilia Romagna. One of the themes was rural change and foodscapes. The policies of the Regione Emilia Romagna aim for an increase of organic and integrated production and strengthening the regional food systems. Rimini organises a collaborative process for its strategic plan in which the aspect of food planning can be strengthened.

The forum aims to approach this in an integrated landscape based way, addressing the following questions: (1) Who are the main stakeholders in the regional food system? (2) How are the food production areas linked to the coastal urbanised areas and its permanent or temporary (tourists) consumers? (3) What are the main challenges for developing a sustainable food system in the area that considers policies for climate change, sustainable tourism, and inclusion? (4) How to balance global production with local production? And (5) Which spatial strategies can help to develop the food system in a sustainable way?

A working party of academics and master students with the support of local experts studied the area focusing on the transect from the inland to the coast between Cesena and Cesenatico. The process consisted of studying references, a study visit to the focus area with meetings with local producers.

In this paper we evaluate and present the main outcomes of the forum for the development of sustainable foodscapes, the role of the forum in the planning process of local and regional authorities and the way an integrated landscape approach can contribute to sustainable food planning, together with the advantages and disadvantages of long-term in depth studies with pressure cooking sessions such as the forum, where the input of an multi-cultural, international group of participants can generate new concepts. The paper concludes with how the study of a focus area, using a transect can generate transferable knowledge for transformative approaches for sustainable food planning.

Towards healthy, sustainable and regional foodscapes: A landscape design perspective

Noël van Dooren

This paper discusses a series of design studios on interventions in food systems. It is shown how these interventions can be understood as contributions to the transition towards a sustainable food system, and it is shown how design outcome, and the reflection on it, can help the understanding of that transition to be area-specific.

Tourism Development and the Urbanization of Food Spaces: Changing Foodscapes in the Western Ligurian Riviera, Italy

Sebastian Felipe Burgos Guerrero

The historical absence of food from the urban agenda, has given rise to renewed attention from scholars and practitioners on the role food can play in the way we plan and conceptualize the urban, with a growing emergence and integration of food policies and strategies, innovative governance structures and alternative food geographies.

'Foodscapes' are now starting to be used as a key term and concept to analyse and give sense to the complex realities of food systems, with systemic approaches addressing the interconnected social and spatial dimensions of these spaces. The past 70 years have witnessed a substantial and widespread modification of foodscapes connected to changing land-use patterns, urban-rural migrations and highly differentiated spatial-temporal movements, concentrations, and use of resources by a growing 'urban' population. This article aims to provide a theoretical framework for the implications of the significant transformations of foodscapes connected to evolving tourism developments and urbanization processes, shedding light on the specific case study of the Western Ligurian Riviera in Italy. In doing so, this study attempts to analyse and map the main social and spatial characteristics and transformations, outlining potential opportunities, challenges, and possible scenarios for the future.

Keywords – Food Planning, Tourist Spaces, Landscape Transformatio

Poster Presentations

INSUAH - Integrated Study on Urban Agriculture as Heritage

Katharina Christenn, Frank Lohrberg

Given the global challenges of urbanization, limited resources and food security within the last 20 years Urban Agriculture has turned from a phenomenon experienced as exotic to a globally recognized instrument for a sustainable development. Urban Agriculture is acknowledged as a panacea to implement the Sustainable Development Goals. However, the focus of Urban Agriculture initiatives is mostly in creating new systems, the qualities of old and ongoing systems of agricultural production and food provision are not raised systematically. Urban agricultural heritage and urban food systems as heritage are clearly understudied.

Today, facing manifold global changes, being aware of the past, is more needed than ever. In this transition it is helpful to revisit historic examples of urban agriculture and urban food systems, especially if they have survived up to today. What are the benefits of traditional, vernacular forms of urban agriculture for food supply, income generation, social diversity and biodiversity, and the urban metabolism?

To answer this question, first steps could be made with the International Herrenhausen Conference “Urban Agricultural Heritage and the Shaping of Future Cities” funded by the Volkswagen in May 2019 and the following book project “Urban Agricultural Heritage”. It became quite obvious that Urban Agricultural Heritage is a missing link to fully unfold Urban Agriculture’s potential for SDG 11. In particular, research has to overcome a Eurocentric, “top-down” heritage understanding and planning paradigms which are still dominated by Western urbanization concepts.

The project INSUAH, coordinated by the Institute of Landscape Architecture at RWTH Aachen University, now allows to tie in the conference’s findings and conduct a first Integrated Study on Urban Agriculture as Heritage. INSUAH delves in 5 global cases, Sao Paulo, Havana, Bandung, Tokyo, and Nuremberg. The consortium comes from planning disciplines and human ecology and is experienced in an applied, transdisciplinary and transformative research. The project combines historical investigations, spatial analysis and living lab methods. It will detect, map and define the heritage and its values and threats, raise awareness for the heritage, and elaborate targeted planning and policy agendas.

INSUAH will exchange the twin-study findings from three continents and integrate them in a parallel meta-level process by focussing on a living heritage approach and taking an ecosystematic, contextual, and participatory perspective. Finally, INSUAH will formulate a SDG 11.4 orientated agenda on Urban Agricultural Heritage together with global players in this field like FAO, RUAF and UN Habitat.

Self-production of food in Norman allotments: what contribution to the local food system?

Léna Jégat

Urban agriculture is most often studied from the perspective of its social (Giacchè et al., 2017), environmental (Den Hartigh, 2013), or urban planning (Consalès, 2004) functions. However, relatively little research focuses on its food functions (Pourias et al., 2015; Marie, 2019). Similarly, gardening practices have often been interrogated through the lens of historical and majoritarian profiles (Pluvinaige et al., 1992), with only a few recent studies focusing on the specific practices of minority populations, often with immigrant backgrounds (Hochedez, 2018).

The paper proposes to question the contribution of allotment gardens (groupings of vegetable plots, intended for households from working-class groups) to the local food system from two points of view. Firstly, from a food perspective: how can the vegetable production of these collective gardens help to feed the city in a healthy and sustainable way? Secondly, from a social point of view: how can this self-production of food provide an answer to the diversity of food cultures?

The results presented in this paper, stemming from a thesis in progress, are based on a varied approach. First of all, a spatial analysis work, via the detailed digitization of 3,200 allotment garden plots of three Norman agglomerations (Rouen, Caen and Alençon) which allowed to estimate the surface occupied by these gardens and to calculate a cultivation ratio in order to distinguish their functional tendency: food production (70% of the plots) or leisure (30% of the plots). Crossed with the harvest diary survey of 30 beneficiaries (2021 harvests), these data made it possible to estimate the weight of the annual harvests and the yield of the allotment plots. Finally, a comparison with local food consumption allows us to estimate the contribution of vegetable production from this form of urban agriculture.

The survey of the beneficiaries of allotment gardens makes it possible to question a discourse that goes beyond the simple weight of the harvests: the attachment to the land of households from more or less recent immigration whose agricultural or peasant origins are still close. The garden allows them to cultivate varieties from their region of origin (often family seeds), allowing for a supply of special products, in line with their food cultures, which are not widely available on the market, as illustrated by this gardener from Cambodia (Alençon, 2021): "Water bindweed, we really use a lot of it for cooking, we can only buy it in Paris, and it's 17€ a bunch!".

What's cooking in Almere? Avoiding, adapting or adopting flavours from other cultures

Sara Smaal, Esther Veen

The city of Almere is often portrayed as a melting pot of cultures, a Dutch miniature version of a multi-ethnic city. As a consequence of globalisation and migration, more and more cuisines are gradually making their way into the foodscape of Almere, some more visible than others. To what extent are the citizens of Almere able to find and enjoy the foods and dishes they identify with - or simply enjoy eating - in Almere's shops and restaurants? And to what extent do they encounter and are they open to try or adopt tastes and cuisines from cultures other than their own? On this poster, we present the results of an online survey that we are conducting in Almere this summer. Residents of Almere are asked to reflect on how often they eat meals from cuisines of other countries and cultures, their willingness and curiosity to try unfamiliar foods (using the Food Neophobia Scale), and the extent to which they alter dishes to adjust to taste preferences. We also ask for limitations in terms of availability of products. We may decide to complement this data with interviews held with first generation immigrants who have settled in Almere. In these interviews, participants are asked to reflect on the role food from their home countries plays in their daily lives and how their food routines have changed since moving to the Netherlands. With this exploratory study, we hope to uncover novel, inclusive and place-based ways to increase the accessibility of culturally appropriate and diverse foods in the city of Almere.

Book Presentations

The Hybrid Governance of Urban Food Movements. Learning from Toronto and Brussels.

Alessandra Manganelli

The scope of my contribution is to present and promote a recently published book, titled “the Hybrid Governance of Urban Food Movement. Learning from Toronto and Brussels” (Springer Series on Urban Agriculture). This book offers an original and nuanced analysis of the urban milieu as epicentre of food activism and food governance. The theoretical contribution of the book is to develop a novel conceptual framework that conceptualises key governance tensions experienced by urban food movements in their life-course and development. This is done by drawing from traditions of research on social innovation and collective action, sociological-institutionalist and multi-scalar approaches to governance, political economy, and political ecology perspectives. These lenses are used to revise and reinterpret in a systematic way key strands of the contemporary debate on the governance of urban food movements. Doing so, the book identifies three types of governance tensions urban food initiatives experience as they develop in diverse ways and seek to change food systems and their related socio-political conditions: these tensions are summarised as resource-related, organisational and institutional types of governance tensions.

The empirical contribution of the book is to develop a fine grained analysis of these tensions through examples of food movements in the city-regions of Toronto and Brussels – but also through other cases around the world. Thus, the author investigates urban food movements as they negotiate access to land in urban areas (land-resource governance tensions), build resilient food network organisations (organisational governance tensions), and develop supportive policies and empowering institutions for urban food governance (institutional governance tensions). Through the analysis of these tensions, the book effectively puts real-life challenges of urban food movements in the spotlight—challenges that are increasingly visible and pertinent in today’s converging climate, socio-political, and health crises. Also focusing on ways to cope with the tensions in a reflexive and strategic way, the book offers suggestions to improve alternative food practices and, ultimately, to design promising pathways to instigate food system change.

Small-Scale Soil-less Urban Agriculture in Europe

Silvio Caputo, Valentina Manente

Urban agriculture is one of the most effective strategies to shorten food production and supply chains while increasing food security levels, improving urban ecosystems, accruing mental and physical benefits, and more. Yet urban agriculture models are rarely designed to be integrated on an urban neighbourhood scale, both spatially and as an integral, permanent component of urban life. City farms, community gardens and allotments are on the rise, and they offer opportunities to individuals and local groups to engage with this practice. However, it can be assumed that they are still not collectively perceived as places that provide a necessary public service (e.g., social support) or that enable the fulfilment of a basic right (i.e., food). This presentation documents a model of urban agriculture integrated at a neighbourhood level, which uses food waste collection as a leverage to root food within the broader community life and the local economy.

In the UK, in 2018, 6.4Mt of post-farm gate food was uneaten, with a total value of £19bn and with households responsible for 71% of this uneaten food (WRAP, 2021). Anaerobic digestion (AD) converts food waste into biogas and fertiliser. A pilot project of food waste recycling through anaerobic digestion in a London social housing estate with over 2,000 residents was implemented by a small AD enterprise. Their ultimate goal was to design a new model of waste food recycling and food production, which can sensitise the local community to collect food waste, process it, and use the by product to grow food within the grounds of the estate. At full capacity, the compost and digestate locally generated could fertilise more than 3,000 m² of green areas and rooftops and generate sufficient income to employ gardeners and allow residents to either grow food or benefit from locally grown, healthy, and affordable food grown by the employed farmers. The presentation shows the engagement process of the local community and stakeholders and quantifies its economic viability and the positive impact on the residents and their environment of the model.

Urban Agricultural Heritage

Katharina Christenn, Frank Lohrberg, Axel Timpe, Ayca Sanncar

Urban Agricultural Heritage

The Institute of Landscape Architecture, in cooperation with Volkswagen Foundation and Birkhäuser is publishing the research and practice book “Urban Agricultural Heritage” in Summer 2022. This book project is the first comprehensive approach to the phenomenon of urban agricultural heritage and will be the first to deliver a global survey of projects and initiatives dealing with traditional forms of food production in cities.

New perspectives on the development of Urban Agricultural Heritage

Urban gardening and urban agriculture have become important elements of sustainable urban planning in the face of ongoing urbanization and limited resources - but a consideration of their cultural-historical dimension has been lacking. In many parts of the world, the benefits of agricultural heritage are not fully appreciated - with regard to its unique, irreplaceable values - and it is thus sometimes neglected or even destroyed. It is still not widely understood that urban agriculture is not a new discipline, but one with a long-established history.

The editors present the first comprehensive synopsis of traditional forms of food production in cities and safeguard their valuable knowledge. Based on current research, they develop new perspectives and directions for dealing with urban agriculture worldwide. The book frames the issue of urban agricultural heritage by linking it to the different dimensions “historical research and food policies”, “the concept of cultural memory and practice”, “the concept of cultural landscape” and by showcasing and reflecting active heritage approaches as well as informal/local approaches to urban agricultural heritage.

Scientists, experts from international organisations and civil society representatives approach the theme from different perspectives leading to a better understanding and increased academic awareness of the agricultural heritage of cities. Case studies show examples, including how food production systems with heritage value can be developed and reframed as contributions towards the sustainable cities of the future.

“Urban Agricultural Heritage” is informed by the knowledge, discussions, insights, the questions posed and the lessons learnt from the International Herrenhausen Conference „Urban Agricultural Heritage and the Shaping of Future Cities“ organized in Hannover in May 2019, by RWTH Institute of Landscape Architecture and funded by Volkswagen Foundation.

